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Formulation and evaluation of taste masked oral disintegrating tablet of ondansetron hydrochloride

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ABSTRACT

The demand for mouth dissolving tablets has been growing, during the last decade especially for geriatric and pediatric patients because of swallowing difficulties. The purpose of this research was to mask the intensely bitter taste of Ondansetron HCl and to formulate an orodispersible of the taste-masked drug. Taste masking was done by complexing Ondansetron HCl with different resins like Tulsion 335, Indion 254, Kyron T 134, and Doshion P 514 in different ratio 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 (% w/w) with solvent evaporation method and evaluated by physical and chemical method. Further DRC formulated as oral dispersible tablets and evaluated for patient palatability & disintegration time.

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Introduction:^{1,2}

In recent decades, a variety of pharmaceutical research has been conducted to develop new dosage forms. Considering quality of life, most of these efforts have been focused on ease of medication. Among the dosage forms developed to facilitate ease of medication, the orodispersible tablet is one of the most widely employed commercial products. Orodispersible tablets are better choice in the pediatric, geriatric and developmentally disabled patients who may face difficulty in swallowing conventional tablets or capsules and liquid orals or syrup, leading to ineffective therapy, with persistent nausea, sudden episodes of allergic attacks, or coughing for those who have an active life style, because of their conveniences in term of their self administration. There are some different method available for formulation of orodispersible tablet like disintegrant addition, Freeze Drying Moulding, Sublimation, Spray-Drying, Mass-Extrusion, Direct Compression & some of the patented techniques like Zydis Technology, Durasolv Technology, Orasolv Technology, Flash Dose Technology, Wowtab Technology, Flashtab Technology.

The development of orodispersible tablets also provides an opportunity for a line extension in the market place. A wide range of drug can be considered candidates in this dosage form. Compared to conventional tablets orally disintegrating tablets may show faster action by reducing disintegration Time®. Because orally Disintegrating tablets disintegrating within the oral cavity, patients may reflect the dose from it is in bitter in taste so, here the taste mask of bitter drug is necessary. Taste masking of bitter drug can be done by techniques like, Coating of drug particles with inert agents, Formation of inclusion complexes, Molecular complexes of drug with other chemicals, Solid dispersion system, Microencapsulation, Multiple Emulsions, Using Liposome's, Prodrugs, Mass extrusion method (Dispersion coating) & Ion Exchange Resin.

Ondansetron HCl is competitive serotonin type 3 receptor antagonist. It is effective in the treatment of nausea and vomiting caused by cytotoxic chemotherapy drugs, including cisplatin, and has reported anxiolytic and neuroleptic properties. It is also used in early onset of alcoholism. Generally emesis is preceded with nausea and in such condition it is difficult to administer drug with a glass of water; hence it is beneficial to administer such drugs as orodispersible. Ondansetron HCl is an intensely bitter drug; hence, if it is incorporated directly into an orodispersible the main objective behind formulation of such a dosage form will definitely get futile. Thus in the present study an attempt has been made to mask the taste of Ondansetron Hcl and to formulate orodispersible with good mouth feel so as to prepare a "patients friendly dosage form."

The present research work was aimed at developing taste masked oral disintegrating tablets of Ondansetron Hydrochloride dihydrate employing ion exchange resins with different disintegrating agent and sweetener as diluents. So, here we used different kind of ion exchange resin to mask its bitter taste. These are water insoluble cross-linked polymer containing salt forming groups. It form complex through weak ionic bond with oppositely charged drug. Dissociation of this complex does not occur under salivary pH, so, there is no chance to release drug in mouth & ence bitter taste is masked. Then this drug resin complex was compressed in tablets by adding different disintegrants like crosspovidone, sodium starch glycolate, & Croscarmellose sodium & sweetener as diluents to see its mouth feel properties.

Material and methods:

The present research work was carried out in Cadila Pharmaceutical Ltd. Dholka, Ahmedabad. Ondansetron HCl was obtained from Cadila pharmaceutical Ltd. (Ankleswar), Kyron T 134(Corel Pharma chem, Ahmedabad), Dhoshion (Dhoshion Ltd. Ahmedabad), Tulsion 335(Thermax Ltd., Pune), Indion 254(Ion exchange ,

India Ltd. Mumbai), All other chemicals used in the study were of analytical grade.

Preparation of drug resin complex³

An accurately weighed amount of resin particles were suspended in deionised Water for 15 min. to allow uniform swelling of polymer, after which Ondansetron HCl was added and slurry was stirred with the help of Magnetic stirrer for 45 min to allow the maximum adsorption of drug on to the resin. Resinate thus formed was filtered and washed with deionised Water. It was then dried at 50°C and the drug content was determined Spectrometrically at 216nm.

Evaluation of taste of resinate⁴

Taste of resinate was checked by time intensity method. For this purpose 10 human volunteers were selected. In this method a sample equivalent to a normal dose was held in mouth for 10 seconds and volunteers were asked to evaluate the resinate for taste. Bitterness levels were recorded immediately according Strong Biter (*), Moderate Bitter (#), Slight Bitter (Ψ), Threshold Bitter (\$), & Tasteless (Ω). These volunteers were instructed not to swallow the granules, which were placed on the tongue. They were instructed to thoroughly gargle their mouth with distilled water after the completion of test. The results are shown in Table – 1.

Determination of Drug content.⁵

Ondansetron resinate (100 mg) was placed in a beaker to which 0.1 N HCl (100 ml) was added for eluting Ondansetron from the resinate. The eluate was decanted and replaced with the same volume of fresh eluent. The volume of eluate was measured and assayed for the content of Ondansetron by spectrophotometry (Shimadzu) at wavelength of 216 nm. The elution process was stopped when the absorbance of the last eluate was between 0.2 to 0.8. The sum of the content of Ondansetron in each eluate was equal to the total content of Ondansetron in resinate.

Characterization of DRC.^{6, 5, 16}

The infrared spectra of Ondansetron HCl, Kyron T 134 and drug: resin complex shown in Figure-1. Drug spectrum shows prominent peaks at 3375.57 cm⁻¹, 1693.57 cm⁻¹, 1458.26 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the -NH stretching, C=O and CH₂ & CH₃ deformation respectively. Kyron T 134 shows a characteristic peak at 1702.25 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O stretching of aryl acids. Drug: resin complex spectrum shows absence of characteristic drug peaks at 3375.57cm⁻¹. Subtraction spectrum did not show the characteristic peak of drug at 3375.57 cm⁻¹ corresponding to -NH stretching. This indicates interaction of amine group of drug with Kyron T 134.

Physical Properties of the Tablet Blend⁷

Physical properties such as bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, and the angle of repose of blend were determined. Bulk density was determined by the USP method I, tapped density was determined by USP method II. Percent compressibility was calculated using following Equation.

Percent compressibility = $\{(D_t - D_b) / D_t\} \times 100$
Where, D_t and D_b are tapped and bulk densities. The results are shown in Table - 3.

Evaluation of Tablets:

The orodispersible tablets were compressed on 18 station compression machine (Karnavati Eng. Ltd.) & evaluated for hardness, weight variation, thickness, friability and drug content. Hardness of the tablets was tested using a Strong- Cobb hardness tester (Rimek, Kadi, Gujarat, India). Friability of the tablets was determined in a Roche friabilator (Electrolab EF-2, India). The thickness of the tablets was measured by vernier calliper (Mitituyo Corp., Japan). Weight variation test was performed according to the official method. The results are shown in table – 4.

Wetting Time and Water absorption ratio⁸

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish (internal diameter of 5.5 cm)

containing 6 ml of water. A tablet was placed on the paper and the time required for complete wetting was measured. The wetted tablet was then weighed. Water absorption ratio 'R' was determined using the Following equation,

$$R = 100 (W_a - W_b) / W_b$$

Where, W_b is weight of tablet before water absorption.

W_a is weight of tablet after water absorption.

In vitro Disintegration Time:^{9,10}

In vitro disintegration time for ODTs was determined using USP disintegration apparatus with SSF (pH 6.2) as the disintegrating medium.

In vitro Dissolution studies:^{12,13,14}

The *In vitro* dissolution studies were carried out using USP apparatus type II (paddle) at 50 rpm. The dissolution medium used was 0.1 N HCl (500ml) maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Aliquots of dissolution media were withdrawn at different time intervals and content of Ondansetron Hydrochloride was measured by determining absorbance at 216 nm. The dissolution experiments were conducted in triplicate. The dissolution profiles are shown in figure – 3 & 4.

Comparison of Optimized Formulation with Conventional Marketed Tablet¹⁶

In vitro Dissolution studies for optimized formulation and conventional marketed tablet (Zofran ODT®) were also carried out. Results are shown in figure – 2.

Results and discussion

Physical Properties of the Tablet Blend

The tablet blend of all the batches was evaluated for different derived properties viz- angle of repose (between 23 to 28), bulk density (between 0.53 to 0.56 gm/ml), Compressibility index (between 13 to 16). The results angle of repose and compressibility indicated that the flowability of blend is significantly good. All the tablets passed weight variation test as the percent weight

variation was within the pharmacopoeial limits. Hardness was shown in the range of 3.51 ± 0.38 to 4.02 ± 0.63 kg/cm² all the formulations. The hardness of all tablets was kept within the above mentioned range to compare the disintegration time between the formulations prepared using different disintegrants and their varying concentrations. The friability of all formulations was determined. The friability values of none of the formulations exceeded 1%. The results of friability indicate that the tablets were mechanically stable and can withstand rigors of transportation and handling. Thickness of all tablets was 3.13 ± 0.08 to 3.21 ± 0.02 mm showing fairly uniform tableting. The results of disintegration values were found to be in the range of 8.21 ± 1.08 to 61.23 ± 1.89 sec. The wetting time and water absorption time was found between 14.8 ± 0.88 to 82.2 ± 2.78 sec and 76.48 ± 0.44 to 86.86 ± 0.16 . The time intensity study for taste in human volunteers of both the DRC and ODT revealed considerable masking of the bitter taste of Ondansetron HCl with degree of bitterness below the threshold value (0.5) ultimately reaching to 0 within 15 minutes. Sensory evaluation of the optimized tablet proved good palatability.

Drug Release from ODT

All the tablets prepared were subjected for release profile. All the tablets of F1 to F9 batch showed a drug release between 98 to 100 % within 12 minutes. Among nine batches, batch F6 which contain MCC and Mannitol in 1:1 ratio along with 9 mg of crospovidone was selected as optimized batch because of its lowest disintegration time and highest drug release. The drug release of the marketed product and F6 formulation was found to be 91.48 ± 2.23 and 100.12 ± 1.98 at the end of 12 minutes. From the above observations, it may be concluded that optimized formulation is better than marketed conventional tablet in release rate of drug. But because of the high amount MCC it had a less mouth peel effect so further formulation batches F10 to F13 were taken for evaluation of

Mouth peel Property of tablet by taking different ratio of Mannitol & MCC.

Mouth peel property

Tablet obtained from the F6 (6% crospovidone) have satisfactory result (means 8.21±1.08 sec D.T) but it feels grittiness in the mouth. Batch No.

F11 (6% crospovidone along with Mannitol:MCC ratio 90:10 is found to be have good mouth peel property & disintegration (11.56±1.21 sec). It was observed that increase in Mannitol:MCC ratio also increase disintegration time.

Table - 1 : Taste evaluation of Drug resin complex

Volunteers	Complex											
	Drug:Tulsion 335			Drug:Kyron T 134			Drug:Indion 254			Drug:Doshion P 514		
	1:1	1:2	1:3	1:1	1:2	1:3	1:1	1:2	1:3	1:1	1:2	1:3
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12
1	*	#	Ψ	#	Ψ	Ω	#	#	\$	*	#	Ψ
2	*	#	\$	#	Ψ	Ω	*	Ψ	Ω	*	#	Ψ
3	*	#	Ψ	#	\$	Ω	#	#	Ω	*	#	#
4	#	#	Ψ	#	Ψ	Ω	#	Ψ	\$	#	#	Ψ
5	#	Ψ	Ψ	Ψ	Ψ	Ω	#	#	Ω	*	#	Ψ
6	*	#	Ψ	#	\$	Ω	*	#	\$	*	Ψ	Ψ
7	#	#	\$	#	Ψ	Ω	#	Ψ	\$	#	#	Ψ
8	#	Ψ	Ψ	#	Ψ	Ω	#	Ψ	Ω	*	#	Ψ
10	*	#	\$	#	\$	Ω	*	#	Ω	*	Ψ	\$

Table – 2: Formulation composition of ODT

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13	F14
DRC	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8	44.8
Mannitol (Perlitol)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
MCC (RQ 102)	44.5	43.7	43	44.5	43.7	43	44.5	43.7	43	51.6	60.2	68.8	77.4	86
Croscarmellose Sodium	44.5	43.7	43	44.5	43.7	43	44.5	43.7	43	34.4	25.8	17.2	8.6	**
Crospovidone	6	7.5	9	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
Sodium Starch Glycolate	**	**	**	6	7.5	9	**	**	**	9	9	9	9	9
Aspartame	**	**	**	**	**	**	6	7.5	9	**	**	**	**	**
Magnesium Stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Sodium stearyl fumarate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Aerosil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Flavour color	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

DRC is equivalent to a 8 mg of Ondansetron

Table – 3: Physical Properties of Tablet Blend

Formulation No.	Bulk Density (gm/ml)	Tapped Density (gm/ml)	Angle of Repose (°) *	% Compressibility	HR
F1	0.549	0.632	25.23±0.45	13.13	1.15
F2	0.554	0.658	28.29±0.72	15.8	1.18
F3	0.541	0.643	24.61±0.62	15.86	1.18
F4	0.529	0.627	26.31±0.38	15.62	1.18
F5	0.536	0.634	24.86±0.81	15.45	1.18
F6	0.549	0.638	26.32±0.57	13.94	1.16
F7	0.537	0.621	27.75±0.85	13.52	1.15
F8	0.544	0.635	26.85±0.69	14.33	1.16
F9	0.563	0.651	25.46±0.83	13.51	1.15
F10	0.539	0.621	23.74±0.48	13.2	1.15
F11	0.557	0.648	24.81±0.75	14.04	1.16
F12	0.568	0.671	23.78±0.49	15.35	1.18
F13	0.553	0.649	26.52±0.76	14.79	1.17
F14	0.548	0.643	25.57±0.82	14.77	1.17

*

Mean±SD (n=3)

Table - 4: Physical Properties of Tablet

Formulation No.	Friability *	Hardness (kg/cm ²) #	Thickness (mm) #	Weight Variation (mg) \$	Disintegration Time (sec) *	Wetting Time (sec) *	% Water absorption *
F1	0.36±0.45	3.67±0.32	3.16±0.03	151±1.53	44.66±1.52	75.7±2.15	82.65±0.45
F2	0.39±0.13	3.75±0.25	3.13±0.08	149±1.39	26.33±0.57	48.8±1.29	78.98±0.89
F3	0.41±0.29	3.83±0.89	3.18±0.02	152±1.84	14.33±1.15	25.6±1.12	76.48±0.44
F4	0.38±0.43	3.75±0.65	3.16±0.09	153±1.08	37.58±1.13	61.4±1.64	81.98±0.86
F5	0.40±0.26	3.66±0.15	3.21±0.02	151±1.14	17.85±0.92	32.1±0.96	78.45±1.14
F6	0.43±0.38	3.72±0.58	3.20±0.08	152±1.38	8.21±1.08	14.8±0.88	79.59±0.65
F7	0.33±0.28	3.51±0.38	3.14±0.05	149±1.56	61.23±1.89	82.2±2.78	83.13±0.53
F8	0.35±0.17	3.76±0.81	3.17±0.09	152±1.92	35.48±1.76	69.3±1.66	79.15±0.49
F9	0.38±0.19	4.02±0.63	3.16±0.05	153±1.51	22.37±1.89	39.4±1.55	76.87±0.38
F10	0.39±0.41	3.82±0.79	3.14±0.03	152±1.46	9.56±1.37	16.85±0.73	81.56±1.62
F11	0.43±0.36	3.71±0.58	3.21±0.07	152±1.65	10.13±1.57	17.86±0.59	82.42±0.74
F12	0.36±0.28	3.63±0.82	3.16±0.04	151±1.81	10.93±1.64	18.17±0.74	83.14±1.02
F13	0.35±0.61	3.76±0.71	3.17±0.02	151±1.73	11.56±1.21	18.25±0.87	84.96±0.84
F14	0.32±0.24	3.75±0.57	3.18±0.06	149±1.65	14.55±1.18	19.55±1.17	86.86±0.16

(Mean±SD) * n=3, # n=6, \$ n=20

Figure-1: Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of (A) Ondansetron HCl, (B) Kyron T 134 & (C) DRC.

Figure-2: *In vitro* release profile of different Formulation.

Figure-3 : Mean dissolutin time of different formulation.

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrated complete taste masking of Ondansetron HCl and rapid disintegration and dissolution of ODT. Taste masking and rapid disintegration of tablets formulated in this investigation may possibly help in administration of Ondansetron HCl in a more palatable form without water during emesis. Thus, the “patient-friendly dosage form” of bitter drugs, especially for pediatric, geriatric, bedridden, and non co-operative patients, can be successfully formulated using this technology.

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